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HPC INNOVATION FOR EUROPEAN SMES

Innovating and Widening the HPC use and skills base

Project Number: 951745

D5.1

Dissemination, Communication and Collaboration Plan

Updated version, December 2022

EuroHPC
Joint Undertaking

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List of abbreviations

#	number
AI	Artificial Intelligence
DIH(s)	Digital Innovation HUB(s)
CSA	Coordination and Support Action
CC	Competence Centre
DoA	Description of Action
EC	European Commission
EuroCC	European project (RIA) dedicated to the establishment of National Competence Centres in HPC, HPDA and AI (2020-2022)
FF, FF2	Fortissimo and Fortissimo 2 project
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
HPC	High-Performance Computing
HPDA	High-Performance Data Analysis
INFRAG	Infrastructure Advisory Group (EuroHPC JU)
IP	Intellectual Property
ISBN	International Standard Book Number
ISV(s)	Independent Software Vendor(s)
JU	Joint Undertaking, here: EuroHPC JU
KPIs	Key Performance Indicators
Mx	Project month
NCC	National Competence Centre
RIAG	Research and Innovation Advisory Group (EuroHPC JU)
ROI	Return on Investment
SME	Small and medium-sized enterprise
VI	Visual Identity
WP	Work Package
Yx	Project year

Note

All dissemination material available to public must contain the following statement and a disclaimer when appropriate.

Statement:

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Executive Summary

This document describes the initial plan for dissemination, communication and collaboration for the FF4EuroHPC project. This plan is a vivid document and thus will be constantly updated on the basis of the project progress. Since the D5.1 submission in November 2020, the first update followed in November 2021 and the last one in December 2022. More detailed KPIs (Key Performance Indicators) are added to measure the performance of certain activities during shorter time frames. A short summary of update is added after the presentation of each task.

The plan is presented as per defined activities of Work Package 5 (WP5¹) with Milestones and/or KPIs and due time frame as defined in the project DoA.

¹ WP5: Success stories, Dissemination to and interaction with the HPC Ecosystem

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1 Introduction

The overall objective of FF4EuroHPC is to enable the European industry to be more competitive globally by using advanced HPC services (including Simulation, Data Analytics and/or Artificial Intelligence). FF4EuroHPC will achieve this objective by realising the goals of:

- Making advanced HPC services accessible to industrial users, particularly SMEs, through competences available in the project and the experiments.
- Create, publish and distribute success stories to show the full potential of these advanced HPC services.
- Promoting and scaling the business impact through the entire SME ecosystem.

WP5, will, in collaboration with other WPs, support the achievement of this objective by creating awareness of the business benefits of advanced HPC Services across the whole value chain encompassing end-users, service providers, ISVs, HPC/HPDA/AI experts and providers of HPC-Infrastructure.

Three main tasks are defined in WP5:

- Task 5.1 – Outreach, Communication, and Dissemination
- Task 5.2 – Success Stories
- Task 5.3 – Collaboration with EuroHPC and other entities

Within WP5, five deliverables will be submitted. The first deliverable D5.1 refers to the current document and was submitted in November 2020, followed by the second D5.2 First Dissemination, Communication and Collaboration Report in February 2022 and D5.4 Success Story Booklet 1st edition in November 2022. The last two deliverables D5.3 Final Dissemination, Communication and Dissemination Report and D5.5 Success Story Booklet 2nd edition will be provided by M36.

Tasks and deliverables will be presented in detail in the following chapters together with the dissemination plan including milestones, performance indicators, and the due time frame.

2 Dissemination, communication and collaboration activities plan

The activities in this Work Package have the objective of ensuring **the maximum amount of awareness** via communication and dissemination in collaboration with relevant Digital Innovation Hubs (DIHs) and industry associations with the aim of **maximising the impact** of the project.

In order to achieve and maximize the dissemination objectives of the project, the dissemination activities need to reach the proper target group, covering diverse industries and European geographic regions.

There were two main areas of communication and dissemination activities:

- 1. Open Call promotion**
- 2. Communication of project activities and dissemination of project results**

Open Call promotion already ended in September 2021 thus the activities related to it were removed from this update and could be found in the D5.2 update V2.

2.1 Communication of project activities and dissemination of project results

The communication of the project activities (goals, developments, benefits, challenges of the experiments) and their results aim to raise awareness of the benefits of using advanced technologies and motivating potential HPC users to approach such methods. The main content of the communication will revolve around experiments, most notably the success stories. For organisations in related industrial sectors, the success stories provide the summarised information about the technical experiment results, helping them to benefit by investigating similar approaches. More generally, the success stories explain the potential business benefits and innovation impact from using advanced HPC services, which can inform a broader range of stakeholders and motivate a wide range of potential HPC users.

The communication target is represented by industrial and commercial HPC user communities, service providers, HPC competence centres, relevant SMEs associations and networks, DIHs and domain specific associations from diverse industrial sectors and different geographic regions:

- General audiences and potential HPC users will be reached through the webpage, social media, newsletters, videos and booklets.
- Specific industrial sectors will be reached through the webpage, tailored flyer (per sector), success stories' videos, articles in sector-specific magazines.
- Specific geographic regions will be covered by national entities such as HPC CC, DIHs and industrial associations.

The plan for the **dissemination** and exploitation of **results** is focused on two channels, supported by WP3, WP4 and WP5:

- **Immediate:** The outcome of each experiment is a solution that has an immediate and direct benefit to the company and great social impact.
- **Long-term:** It is expected that many experiments could lead to modelling, simulation and analytics services with applicability beyond the immediate sphere of the application experiment (show case).

WP5 will support communication and dissemination activities by providing the technical infrastructure and developing appropriate material using input from other WPs in particular WP2 (open calls), WP3 (success stories) and WP4 (exploitation and business models).

A draft stakeholder analysis is given in the Appendix. The analysis was built on target audience work undertaken in the previous Fortissimo projects and will be updated in light of the FF4EuroHPC project.

2.2 Task 5.1: Outreach, communication and dissemination

GOALS:

- To produce high quality, tailored dissemination content
- To build up a strong presence in community events
- To outreach with HPC CCs, HPC relevant DIHs and industry associations.

Dissemination activities will be performed by the participation at other projects' events, at relevant conferences and community meetings, by organizing project workshops and project conferences with invited speakers or presenters, by creating webinars and solid media presence on social media (Twitter and LinkedIn) with regular posts on a weekly basis. To provide successful dissemination on project results, newsletters, press releases and some publications in sectorial magazines have been created.

For each of the above-mentioned dissemination activities adequate materials in terms of size and language (technical, business) will be tailored to reach the respective interest groups.

Definition of the targeted interest groups:

1. Technical: service providers, ISVs, HPC/HPDA/AI experts and providers of HPC-Infrastructure.
2. Business: end users – SMEs, industrial associations and other business stakeholders.

Partners actively participated in different events, presenting project activities and success stories. Additionally, four webinars were organised in collaboration with WP4 to present the first tranche of success stories. Within WP4, collaboration with DIHs and NCCs was running successfully, meanwhile Within WP5, communication with industrial associations, HPC ecosystems, and some of the EU projects was carried on.

Actions for communication activities are summarised in Table 1:

Communication target	Communication means							
	Direct	Indirect	Website	Videos	Press Articles and Materials (including art. in sec. mag.)	News-letter	Events, Conf., Trade fairs, Exhibitions, HPC conf.	Social Media
		Via Hubs and Industry associations						
NCCs	x					x		
DIHs	x					x		
SMEs		x	x	x	x	x	x	
ISVs	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	
Industry associations	x					x		x
EU HPC Ecosystem players	x					x		x
HPC centres	x					x	x	
Commercial HPC providers						x	x	
Press				x	x			
General			x	x	x			

Table 1: Actions for communication and dissemination of project results.

ACTIVITIES:

5.1.1 Evolvement of the FF4EuroHPC brand, by finalizing the logo and design

The new logo and visual identity (VI) were developed and approved by the project coordinator. It is obligatory to use the prepared templates and respect the visual identity guidelines.

Milestones:

The Web page publication, final version of the logo, project brand and design were approved by the project coordinator (USTUTT/HLRS). The project templates for project presentations were approved by the project coordinator. The design template for project brochures, general presentations and flyers were approved by the project consortium.

Time frame: From M1 to M3.

5.1.2 Development of dissemination material

Website, brochure, newsletters, posters, flyers, press releases, publications in trade magazines, scientific publications, generic presentations, social media posts; all tailored to interest groups.

Website

A new official project website was developed in the first months of the project.

The official project website² is the main dissemination interface presenting project activities and results to general public. The page is being regularly updated with news, events, success stories and project activities. All of the project dissemination materials are published on the website. Arctur, as the WP5 leader, is responsible for the website management. Previous Fortissimo project website

² See FF4Euro HPC: <https://www.ff4eurohpc.eu/>

(where the main information on the former FF and FF2 projects are available) is accessible on the www.fortissimo-project.eu domain and is linked to the official FF4EuroHPC website.

The implementation of the website was done in interaction with other WPs: with WP1 (general content), WP2 (open calls), WP3 (success stories).

In the first year of the project, the “Open Call” subpages were updated accordingly to the respected Open Call. Furthermore, the Experiments subpage was created, presenting the first tranche of experiments, and “Partners” subpage, where experiment partners are introduced. The “Experiment” subpage was updated with the second tranche of experiments. In November 2022, new section with the first tranche of Success Stories was added, and the subpage EU HPC Ecosystem was created.

The website is maintained by the project partner Arctur and will also persist after the conclusion of the project.

Key Performance Indicators: Target values are presented in Error! Reference source not found. and Table 3: KPIs for Success stories.

. During the project lifetime the number of webpage visits (# webpage visits) and length of the time spent (#time webpage) on the website will be measured with the aim to monitor the website viewership, popularity, and attractiveness.

Time frame: Additional content will be continuously uploaded from M4 onwards.

Brochure

The brochures (general, for SMEs, for ISVs) are available via the [project website](#). They were created as a first contact point for the interested stakeholders. Brochures were updated three times with the project’s progress.

The project brochure is one of the dissemination materials that can be adapted in terms of size and language (technical, business) to reach the respective interest groups from diverse industries and geographic regions.

Time frame: Three updates were planned for all three brochures by M24. Brochures were successfully updated.

Posters

The project poster can be created over the course of the project in terms of size and language (technical, business) to reach the respective interest groups from diverse industries and geographic regions. The poster will be created to represent the project at different events such as trade fairs, workshops, user group and conferences.

Time frame: The poster will be developed upon request and will be tailored to specific needs. It is planned to create at least three versions of the poster during the lifetime of the project (if needed).

Social Media posts

Posts on the social media channels ([Twitter](#)³ and [LinkedIn](#)⁴) have the goal to increase awareness, traffic on the website and to boost brand engagement. The social media channels used within the project are: Twitter, LinkedIn and [You Tube](#)⁵.

³ See <https://twitter.com/FF4EuroHPC>

⁴ See <https://www.linkedin.com/company/ff4eurohpc>

⁵ See <https://youtu.be/nM0dt4bhmgo>

LinkedIn is one of the largest business social networks, which is build up through partnerships. The LinkedIn page is used to reach the target audiences and build awareness of the FF4EuroHPC project through partnerships and in relevant groups.

A social media [calendar](#)⁶ for scheduling posts was prepared, and a KPI table was set to monitor this activity and to measure the goals which will increase awareness and boost brand engagement.

The guidelines for the dissemination material are available in the Appendix. This should provide a guide for all of the project partners to create suitable content.

Each partner needs to contribute one post for Twitter and one for LinkedIn within a six weeks' frame (refer to the calendar).

Social media content is presented through the week in the following context:

- Success story Mondays: each Monday one FF4EuroHPC success story is presented.
- Experiments Wednesday: each Wednesday one experiment is presented.
- Special / National days: success story covering the special / national day topic is being presented.
- Informing about different HPC related events.
- Sharing the knowledge: HPC related topics, blogs, articles, videos, use cases from other projects, institutes, SMEs.
- Celebration: congratulation on Holidays (also partner's national days).
- Spreading the news of EUROCC project and NCCs success stories.

KPIs:

Twitter: #followers - 300 total, #tweets – 500 total, #tweet impressions – 200 per month

LinkedIn: #posts – 100 in total #followers - 500 total, #unique visitors, #impressions – 200 per month

YouTube: #videos - 6 videos of success stories

According to the KPIs table, planned KPIs were already reached due to very active engagement on social media. To keep the engagement and reach as much potential target groups as possible, we will keep the frequency of posting and put additional effort.

Newsletter

During the project lifetime **five newsletters** were planned to be released. The newsletter is an additional tool to help promoting the project activities and results. It will be linked to other social media channels and uploaded on the project website.

The layout is aligned with the FF4EuroHPC visual identity, it consists of at least three different sections. There is the possibility to subscribe through the MailChimp subscription form implemented on the official webpage. The promotion of subscription to the newsletter is running continuously through the social media, emails, and partner's presentations. Up to date, five issues were already sent and the KPI number of subscribers was already overreached (KPI is 150 subscribers in total, by end-November, there were 172 subscribers).

Within the project lifetime, one or two additional issues of the newsletter will be prepared and published.

KPIs with time frame: To publish a newsletter at least every seven months, and to have up to 100 subscribers at the end of Y1, and 50 more subscribers at the end of Y2 of the project.

⁶ See <https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1qsytmQqUnpzkaLmP3isonWoCg0S1OVynyiMjT44Ei30/edit#gid=0>

Flyers

For each success story a downloadable flyer will be developed. For the first tranche of the success stories, 16 flyers were designed and published next to the story presentation on the website. If needed, updates of the flyers will be created.

KPIs with time frame: refer to **Error! Reference source not found.**

Publication in trade magazines / papers

Partners were asked to promote success stories in sector magazines. This is an additional way to promote the project results in an efficient way. Additionally, NCCs will be asked to help promoting the success stories by translating them into their national languages and publishing them in sector magazines.

KPIs: At least two publications in sector-specific magazines per partner by M36 (ten publications in total).

Press Releases & Press clippings

Press clippings are being collected as a result of the awareness raising and the project results dissemination. Press releases and clippings are the main channel for addressing the general public. The table for Press clipping collection must be filled by partners and is available on the [BSCW portal⁷](#) (ref. to the .xls file “**Metrics_FF4EuroHPC**”). So far, three press releases were already written and shared with media, and one additional will be prepared by the end of the project.

KPIs with time frame: Three press releases, ten articles by M36.

Generic presentations

The project presentation can also be adapted in terms of size and language (technical, business) to reach the respective interest groups from diverse industries and geographical regions. The presentation was created and updated regularly for representing the project and success stories at different events such as trade fairs, workshops, user group, conferences.

KPIs with time frame: the presentation was developed and is tailored / updated according to specific needs.

Conferences, trade fairs and other events

One of the important dissemination activities is attending events which are relevant for promoting the project and its results. The purpose of attending events is also to get in contact with the representatives of the target group. The event plan is prepared on a yearly basis and is updated constantly. Each partner has to inform the WP5 leader about the events they are going to attend (actively or passively) and after that a short reporting about the attended event should be created. Partners presented the project activities and success stories widely during the first and second project year, and will continue to actively present the success stories. The news item about the active participation in the event should be prepared by partner(s), who visited the event. At least one photo from the event should be included,

⁷ BSCW is HLRS shared workspace server. HLRS is FF4EuroHPC project leader.

and link to more information about the event /video recording or event materials should be added. All data and information about the events are collected in the .xls file “Metrics_FF4EuroHPC” which is uploaded on BSCW portal.

KPIs: Active participation at a minimum of five relevant events. So far the KPIs for events are already reached, but partners will continue with project promotion also in the third project year.

Please refer to **Error! Reference source not found.**, in which the KPIs are summarised per communication action:

Communication actions	Target Group	KPI & Target Values	Time Frame
Website	SMEs, General public, Press, Potential open call proposers	#visitors 7,000 #page views 1,500	By M36
Brochure	General public, Innovation centres, Ind. associations, SMEs.	#updates 3 #tailored versions 3	By M24
Poster (on request)	General public, Innovation centres, Ind. associations, SMEs.	#updates 3 #tailored versions 3	By M24
Social Media (Twitter, LinkedIn)	General public, Innovation centres, Ind. associations, SMEs.	#followers total 300 #tweets total 500 #tweet impressions 200	By M36 (50% by M12, 25% more by M24, total by M36)
Newsletters	SMEs, ISVs, Ind. associations, HPC ecosystem	#issues 5 #subscribers 150	Issues every 7M 70% of subscribers by M12
Articles in sector magazines / papers	SMEs	#articles 10	5 by M30, 5 by M35
Press releases	Press	#press releases 3	1 per year
Press clippings	General public	#articles 10	By M36
Visits to trade fairs, user groups, conferences, workshops	SMEs, ISVs	#events 5	Participation to events by M35 70% visits during Y1 and Y2, success stories presentation in Y3

Table 2: KPIs for communication actions.

In order to track all the activities that have been performed, the .xls file “Metrics_FF4EuroHPC” has been created where all partners will be regularly asked to insert information about the communication actions they have performed (events attended, press releases, press clippings).

5.1.3 Production of six success stories videos

It was planned that for each tranche of application experiments (from the two Open Calls), **3 promotional videos** will be produced for the top experiments (6 in total). According to the agreement with all project partners, two videos will be produced for the first tranche and four videos for the second tranche of success stories due to the inequality number of success stories (16 success stories per tranche 1 and 26 success stories per tranche 2). These will be approximately 2-5minute long videos that are also suitable for online or conference presentations. A typical scenario for all videos is: FF4EuroHPC project introduction, short presentation of partners and industrial sector of the experiment, experiment challenges and achievements, benefits of using HPC, HPDA and AI as well as the impact on end-user and/or social impact.

Prior to the actual video shoot, the detailed scenario has to be approved by project partners and from experiment partners. The video will be used for dissemination purposes during the project lifetime and beyond.

The *Video Consent and Release Form* will need to be signed by all involved parties prior to the video shooting.

KPIs: Six videos produced; 2,000 views in total;

Time frame: From M26 to M35.

All planned activities were carried out according to the D5.1 dissemination and communication plan. KPIs were already reached. Some of KPIs were set modestly, and some were over reached due to extensive activity.

2.3 Task 5.2: Success Stories

GOAL Dissemination of “lessons learned” from the usage of advanced HPC services

Success stories are the main outputs of the FF4EuroHPC project and are expected to be delivered by each experiment. A clear presentation of the business benefits for the experiment partners in these stories will be the main focus. This can be used **to achieve broader impact by serving as a role model**. These stories highlight **what can be achieved** using advanced HPC services, and thus **address low awareness** which is a key inhibitor to the take-up of modelling, simulation and analytics solutions by companies that have not used such before.

For organisations in related industrial sectors, the success stories provide summarised information about the technical experiment results. This helps them to benefit by investigating similar approaches. More generally, the success stories explain the potential business benefits and innovation impact from using advanced HPC services, which can inform a broader range of stakeholders and motivate a wide range of potential HPC users.

Within the first Open Call, 16 experiments were carried out and were successfully concluded – they resulted in the success stories. In the second Open Call, 26 experiments were selected for funding and had been running by May 2023. If all will be successful, we can expect to get 26 new success stories. In total, 42 success stories are expected.

The first tranche of success stories were already presented in flyers, booklet and on the website by M26. The second tranche of the success stories will be created and submitted by M34–M35.

ACTIVITIES:

5.2.1 Writing success stories and collecting materials (images, relevant data and content) from the experiments

Each success story is written following **pre-defined templates and scenarios**, that were prepared by WP5 and approved by coordinator and WP3 leader. These focus on the lessons learned and business benefits of the use of advanced technologies and services by end users and other members of the value chain and thereby quantify ROI, time to pay back investment and value of new market created. WP3 will support these activities by contributing contents of the experiments.

To produce success stories for dissemination purposes the following material were collected:

- a) Content/text of success stories written in tailored/dedicated template
- b) At least four images of the experiment in high resolution – min 1200x800 px, .jpg or .png format (team image, technical image1, technical image2, image3).
- c) Data: role of experiment partners (end user, ISV, domain expert, HPC provider), country of end user, name of software used, name of industrial sector.

Success stories creation and dissemination was already presented to the OC1 experiment partners and will be presented also to OC2 experiment partners in January 2022.

In agreement with partners, the content for the success stories presentation remains the same as for Fortissimo. The paragraph on social impact was added, presenting major achievements related to social or environmental sustainability. The design of the booklet and flyers is adjusted according to project's visual identity. Additionally, the technology used in the experiment is highlighted on the top of the booklet together with the country of end-user and industrial sector. In the booklet presentation, success stories are joint by sectors.

5.2.2 Dissemination of the success stories (website, social media, flyers, newsletter, booklet)

All success stories are disseminated through the following communication channels or means: Website, e-flyers, booklet, newsletters, social media (Twitter, LinkedIn, YouTube)

Target groups will be reached via direct and indirect communication channels. In case of an indirect communication, intermediaries (industry associations, hubs) are used to reach the target group (SMEs). In case of a direct communication, there will be no intermediaries. It is a direct communication with the specific representative of the target group (see also **Error! Reference source not found.**: Actions for communication and dissemination of the project results).

All success stories are published in a special section dedicated to this topic on the official project website⁸. For each success story a downloadable flyer (PDF) is generated. There is offered also be a search option to filter stories by sector, by country and by technology. Stories are being presented in the project newsletters and in the social media posts with the aim to raise awareness of what can be achieved in business by using advanced technologies.

⁸ See <https://www.ff4eurohpc.eu/>

Two printed editions (booklets) of the success stories will be generated. Booklets have proven to be an effective means of dissemination for events like trade fairs involving face-to-face contact with potential users who are new to HPC, HPDA and AI with regard to how it can help their businesses. The second edition of the booklet will be equipped with an ISBN code for distribution purposes to relevant and interested European libraries.

KPIs: please refer to Table 3: KPIs for Success stories.

Outputs with ref. to success stories	Target Group	KPIs & Target Values	Time Frame
Website	General public.	#views: 200	From M25 to M36
Downloadable PDF	SMEs, ISVs, general public.	#downloads: 30	From M25 to M36
Booklet (two editions)	SMEs, ISVs (trade fairs)	#500 printed and distributed	1 st ed. by M26 2 nd ed. by M35
Videos	SMEs, general public.	#videos: 6 produced #views: 2,000 in total	From M25 to M36
Newsletter	SMEs, ISVs, Inn. centres, Ind. associations, HPC ecosystem.	To be included in last two issues.	From M25 to M36
Social Media (LinkedIn & Twitter) (YouTube for video)	Inn. centres, SMEs, Ind. associations.	#posts 5 per month #posts 15 (new)	From M25 to M36

Table 3: KPIs for Success stories.

2.4 Task 5.3: Collaboration with EuroHPC and other entities

GOAL: Execution and evaluation of the collaboration with different entities; especially within the EuroHPC

To achieve successful collaborations with different HPC actors, at first those must be catalogued in a comprehensible and clear way. A number of existing materials like the European HPC Handbook⁹, networks of the participating partners and non-confidential results from other projects were exploited, in order to find actors in the European HPC System. After the overview, the evaluation regarding benefit and extent of possible collaboration took place. The outcome of this process was a list of entities suitable for cooperation, which will be divided into target groups and addressed via the appropriate channels. Furthermore, connections to the EUROHPC JU¹⁰ and the governing boards is

⁹ See <https://www.etp4hpc.eu/european-hpc-handbook.html> for more information.

¹⁰ See <https://eurohpc-ju.europa.eu/> for more information.

being established. The representation of the EuroHPC management team at information events will be granted.

Some first steps in this process have already been made, for example presentation to the National Competence Centres (NCCs) in HPC within the EuroCC project¹¹, to DIHs and Centres of Excellences in HPC (CoEs¹²), as well as other European initiatives. This task has regular check-ups to align the measures with the tasks, goals, as well as a series of mechanisms within the working group. Partners will continue to look for new collaborators from 2023 on.

ACTIVITIES:

5.3.1 Identification and Evaluation of potential collaborations

This activity was carried out and included identification, analysis, ROI evaluation, and prioritisation of potential collaborations with entities from industry, European projects, research groups, and others, especially in the frame of EuroHPC.

5.3.2 Creating the collaboration roadmap

On the basis of the results evaluation, a roadmap and a collaboration network, which will need to be maintained, is being generated. Tailored dissemination material will be produced to ensure win – win situations.

5.3.3 Contribution to the EuroHPC JU initiative

This includes exchanging information with the EUROHPC JU on a project level, communicating with the INFRAG or the RIAG governing board and sharing the information about any informative events provided by the EuroHPC Management Team.

5.3.4 Collaboration with national HPC Competence Centres

Collaboration with the NCCs will facilitate the engagement with relevant SMEs and industrial communities in their regions. In the last project year, the success stories will be promoted among NCCs countries.

KPIs: please refer to **Error! Reference source not found..**

KPIs	Target Values	Time Frame
Identification of relevant actors	#15	Until M8
Successful contact uptake	#10	Until M10
Successful collaborations	#5	Until M36

Table 4: KPIs for collaboration with other entities.

¹¹ See <https://www.eurocc-project.eu/> for more information.

¹² See <https://www.hpccoe.eu/> for a description.

3 Conclusion

The dissemination activities are supporting one of the general objectives of FF4EuroHPC, which is to facilitate the widening of industrial HPC user communities and service providers in Europe by delivering compelling success stories for the use of HPC by SMEs; ensuring maximal awareness via communication and dissemination in collaboration with relevant DIHs and industry associations.

WP5 coordinates the dissemination activities with the support and contribution from WP2, WP3, and WP4, addressing the project target groups covering different industries and a broad geographical scope in Europe.

KPIs are associated with the major activities and the progress is being frequently monitored. As the KPIs for the second project year were successfully achieved, the KPIs monitoring is ongoing and is used for communication and dissemination strategy updates. Based on this plan the key activities within the available resources will line up to contribute to the success of the FF4EuroHPC project.

4 References

- [1] WP5: Success stories, Dissemination to and interaction with the HPC Ecosystem
- [2] EuroCC: <https://www.eurocc-project.eu/>
- [3] Digital Innovation Hubs: <https://ec.europa.eu/digital-single-market/en/digital-innovation-hubs>
- [4] In accordance to GDPR
- [5] <https://www.castiel-project.eu/>
- [6] FF4Euro HPC: <https://www.ff4eurohpc.eu/>
- [7] Twitter: <https://twitter.com/FF4EuroHPC>
- [8] LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/ff4eurohpc>
- [9] YouTube: <https://youtu.be/nM0dt4bhmgo>
- [10] Google Docs:
<https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1qsytMoqUnpzkALmP3isonWoCg0S1OVynyiMjt44El30/edit#gid=0>
- [11] BSCW is HLRS shared workspace server. HLRS is FF4EuroHPC project leader.
- [12] <https://www.ff4eurohpc.eu/>
- [13] <https://www.fortissimo-project.eu/>
- [14] European HPC Handbook: <https://www.etp4hpc.eu/european-hpc-handbook.html>
- [15] EuroHPC JU: <https://eurohpc-ju.europa.eu/>
- [16] EuroCC project: <https://www.eurocc-project.eu/>
- [17] HPC CoE: <https://www.hpccoe.eu/>

5 Appendix

5.1 Draft Stakeholder Analysis

Stakeholder	Importance	Benefit for FF4EuroHPC	Benefit for stakeholder	Remarks
Category: Hubs (funded by EU)				
nHPC CCs (national HPC competence centres)	High	Regional outreach	Supports their engagement with SMEs	To be established.
CSA for nHPC CCs	High	Central point of contact for nHPC CCs	Supports their engagement with nHPC CCs	To be established.
Relevant DIH	High	Regional outreach	Supports their work with SMEs	Relevant subset to be selected, ca. 100 with HPC expertise
European HPC Ecosystem players				
PRACE SHAPE	Medium	Outreach to their network	Some stakeholders might be interested in OC	SME programme
EOSC	Medium	Same as above	Some stakeholders might be interested in OC	Has SME programme
ETP4HPC	Medium	Same as above	Increased visibility to industrial end users	None
BDVA	Medium	Same as above	Increased visibility to industrial end users	None
Funding bodies				

EuroHPC JU	High	Visibility and awareness raising	Support for the promotion of the European HPC strategy	None
Category: Industry				
End user: SME with HPC experience	Medium	Raising awareness about FF4EuroHPC in the user communities	Keeping abreast of HPC application developments	Not primarily addressed by the call
End user: SME with computing / simulation experience	High	Potential experiment participants + Raising broad awareness	Potential FF4EuroHPC participation, raised awareness of HPC potential	E.g. using a simulation code on in- house work- stations
End user: SME without computing / simulation experience	High	As above	As above	None
HPC capable ISV	High	Potential experiment participants + Raising awareness about FF4EuroHPC in the HPC ecosystem	Potential FF4EuroHPC participation, awareness of application domain developments	Vendor of HPC- capable software suitable for above SMEs, often part of experiment
HPC / engineering consultants	High	As above	As above	Needed as Application / HPC experts in experiments
HPC centres	High	As above	As above	None
Commercial HPC infrastructure providers	Medium	As above	As above	None
Industry associations	High	As above	Service to their Members: funding opportunities & success stories	E.g. NAFEMS

Category: Academia				
Code owner	Medium	Potential experiment participants + Raising awareness about FF4EuroHPC in the HPC ecosystem	Potential FF4EuroHPC participation, awareness of application domain developments	Research institutes developing HPC codes suitable for SMEs
Application experts	Medium	Potential experiment participants + Raising awareness about FF4EuroHPC in the HPC ecosystem	Potential FF4EuroHPC participation, awareness of application domain developments	Potential partners in experiments
Category: General public				
Press	Medium	Main channel for addressing the General public	Reporting opportunities for leading-edge industrial innovation	None
General public	Medium	Creating positive awareness to influence the continued political support for HPC R&D&I	Understanding the role of HPC in the Digitisation of European Industry and the societal impact arising from many applications	None

5.2 Guidelines for the online dissemination material

1. Social media

1.1 twitter:

Maximum tweet length: 280 characters

Ideal Length of a Tweet: 71-100 Characters

If the post leads to referring page, add link (short link via bitly: <https://bitly.com/>)

Use tags of organisations/SMEs/products, that have a twitter account (use @ - example @ETP4HPC)

Use max 3 hashtags - #FF4EuroHPC, #HPC #AI #HPDA #SME etc.

Add high quality pictures.

1.2 LinkedIn:

Maximum post length: 3,000 characters

Ideal Length of a post: 100 Characters

If the post leads to referring page, add link (short link via bitly: <https://bitly.com/>)

Use tags of organisations/SMEs/products that have LN account (use @ - example @ETP4HPC)

Use max 3 hashtags - #FF4EuroHPC, #HPC #AI #HPDA #SME etc.

Add high quality pictures.

1.3 YouTube:

Video title: 70 characters

Video length: max. of 3 mins (if this is a promo video, success story video)

Photo material – Photos should be provided separately in as a .png

Quality video description, including links and hastaghs

2. News Item

News title: 70 characters

Body text: up to 2,500 characters, black text, no formation

Add at least one high quality photo (min. 1200x800 px, and max. 1800x1200 px)

Video (optional) – video has to be uploaded first on YouTube, and then embedded on the page.

Add links, if needed.

Formats:

Text content: .docx (Word)

Photo material – Photos should be provided separately in .png format

5.3 Project logo and Visual identity

Project logo

Visual identity banner

This banner is adjusted for all of the dissemination material and communication channels – including the website, the social media profiles and the cover photo, the Power Point background, flyers and the newsletter template.

Examples: Social media profile photo.

Example: Website title picture and Social media cover photo.

Example: PPT slide template

5.4 *Success stories templates*

FF4EuroHPC Booklet Template

PAGE 1

Title of the success story

Max 60 characters (with spaces)

Organisations

500 – 600 characters (with spaces)

+ Logos (2-3: End User, HPC Expert, HPC Provider, ISV, ...) and organization URL

+ EU Map with location

The challenge

400 – 450 characters (with spaces)

+ 2 photos (Min 1500 px width/height, 300 dpi resolution)

- Simulation/ end-product / software/ data analytics

PAGE 2

Experiment highlights –

- Industry sector
- Country
- Software used

The solution

450- 500 characters (with spaces)

+ 1 photo production/ team at work

Business and social impact

1.200 – 1.300 characters (with spaces)

Benefits

3-4 bullets, max 100 characters (with spaces) each

FF4EuroHPC Flyer Template

PAGE 1

Title of the success story

Max 60 characters (with spaces)

FF4EuroHPC experiment facts

Industry sector

Country

Software used

Organisations involved

500 – 600 characters (with spaces)

The challenge

600 -800 characters (with spaces)

The solution

600 - 700 characters (with spaces)

Business and social impact

600 – 700 characters (with spaces)

Benefits

600 – 700 characters (with spaces)

The FF4EuroHPC project

650 - 700 characters (with spaces)

Fortissimo Experiment Partners:

Name them + logos

More Information:

Website

Info email

4-5 photos

Min 1500 px width/height, 300 dpi resolution

- Simulation/data analytics
- End-product
- Production / Software
- Team at work

FF4EuroHPC Website Template

Title of the success story

Max 60 characters (with spaces)

+ at least 3 photos (Min 1.500 px width/height, 300 dpi resolution)

- Simulation/data analytics
- End-product
- Production / Software
- Team at work

Organisations

500 – 600 characters (with spaces)

+ PDF Flyer

The challenge

600 -800 characters (with spaces)

The solution

600 - 700 characters (with spaces)

Business and social impact

600 – 700 characters (with spaces)

Benefits

3-4 bullets, max 100 characters (with spaces) each

Organisations involved

Name the organisations